

IMPACT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE ON ANXIETY, DEPRESSION AND STRESS AMONG ADOLESCENTS

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Abstract

The present study intended to analyze the influence of Emotional Intelligence and gender on Anxiety, Depression and Stress. A 2*2*2 factorial design with type of faculty (arts and science) groups of emotional intelligence (high & low)* Gender (boys & girls) was used in present study. A total 120 adolescents (17-21 yrs.) were randomly selected from urban area of Almora city. The emotional intelligence scale was applied to identify the level of emotional intelligence in adolescents. Anxiety, Depression and stress scale was measured the impact of Anxiety, Depression and stress among adolescents. Results revealed that significant effect of emotional intelligence on anxiety, depression and stress. Similarly, emotional intelligence*gender effect was found significant.

Keywords: Adolescent, Anxiety, Depression, Emotional Intelligence, Stress,

Introduction

In today's time, humans are constantly bombarded with a lot of happenings; resulting in various psychological issues like anxiety, stress, depression. Stress, anxiety and depression are important and regular occurrences in college going students. In a study of Anxiety in men and women, college students, found that the female's students had significantly more anxiety than the male students (Devi 1969). In the current competitive environment, students are highly required to develop their right attitude and EI towards unseen complexities of life and to perform multiple roles with efficiency and effectiveness. EI is a subset of social intelligence with the ability to understand and monitor one's own feelings and that of others too. It allows a student to extract the required data for his academic achievement, as well as acquire and maintain social efficiency and effectiveness. Emotional intelligence plays a major role in the development as well as the regression of stress, anxiety and depression. As emotional intelligence helps one to understand how emotions work and to recognize emotions in one's self and others. Good emotional intelligence is usually accompanied by low levels of stress, anxiety and depression. Due to the understanding of emotions in one's self and in that of others, predictions can be made regarding different emotional situations, and how to manage as well as carry one's self during such situations. (Joannan Silman 2018). Medical as well as engineering students are exposed to more stressful conditions, and are more likely to develop stress, depression or anxiety. (Lin Sc, et., 2011).

Objectives of the study:

- 1-To investigate the effect of type of faculty on anxiety, depression and stress.
- 2-To find out the role of gender in Anxiety, Depression and stress.
- 3-To find examine the impact of emotional intelligence on Anxiety, Depression and stress.

Hypothesis of the study:

On the basis of above objectives following Hypothesis were formulated. It was hypothesized that:

- 1-To investigate the effect of type of faculty on anxiety, depression and stress.
- 2-The levels of anxiety, depression and stress also vary in boys and girls.
- 3-Emotional Intelligence would also exercise favorable impact on anxiety, depression and stress.

Method

Design:-

Present study is based on 2×2×2 factorial design with two group of faculty (B.A student and B.S.C student) × Gender (Boy and Girls) × level of emotional Intelligence. (High Emotional Intelligence and Low Emotional Intelligence).

Participants:-

A total of 120 Students age ranged 17-21 yrs. undergraduate students, enrolled in S.S.J campus of Almora city participated in present study. Stratified random sampling technique was used for sample selection. On the basis of median scores obtained on emotional intelligence (mdn=102), student were divided into high emotional intelligence and low emotional intelligence groups.

Measures:-

Anxiety, depression and stress scale (ADSS):

This inventory developed by Bhatnagar et al.,(2011) was used to measure anxiety, depression and stress. The scale contains 48 items related to anxiety (19 items), depression (15 items) and stress (14 items). Response of each item is scored 1 if endorsed yes and 0 if endorsed no. The range of the score is 0-19 for anxiety subscale. 0-15 for depression subscale and 0-14 for stress subscale. Higher score indicates expressing greater anxiety, depression and stress. The reliability coefficient of overall inventory was 0.81 and construct validity of the inventory was 0.86.

Emotional intelligence scale (EIS):

The tool used in emotion intelligence scale is constructed by Singh & Narian (2013). EIS has 31 items. Emotional intelligence Scale measures four dimensions i.e. Understanding Emotions, Understanding Motivation, Empathy, Handling Relations. The answers of those items which tallied with the answers given in the scoring key were of ±1. If they didn't tally, they were given a score of Zero. The reliability coefficient of overall inventory was 0.86 and validity is 0.86.

Procedure

In this study was conducted in two phases. In the 1st phases were students contacted in college setting and request to cooperate. After getting their consent they were briefed about the nature and aims of the study. After receiving the initial willingness their background information were collected on the basis of Personal data sheet (PDS). Then Emotional Intelligence scale was administered one by one and they were requested to response carefully. Students were assured that their response would be kept confidential. After Wards, Students were given an Emotional Intelligence scale and requested to respond carefully. This Emotional Intelligence scale was used to identify the cases of stress high and low emotional intelligence group. Students were further requested to participate in second session of the study. In this session Anxiety, depression and stress was administered to participate individually. After completing their responses they were thanked for cooperation. Data were collected and subjects to computer analysis using SPSS version.

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Results

This section contains results obtained from the statistical analysis of responses obtained on various measures used in this study. The statistical treatment of data was done in terms of comparative analysis (ANOVA). This section deals with ANOVA results.

Comparative (ANOVA) Analysis-

In order to determine the impact of Type of Faculty, Gender and Emotional intelligence on Anxiety, Depression and Stress of adolescents, a 2x2x2 analysis of variance was computed, obtained results are displayed in tables and figures given below.

Impact on Anxiety, Depression and Stress

Table 1.1 displayed Mean and S.Ds of total anxiety, depression and stress. Result (Table 1.1 and Fig 1.1) shows that anxiety, depression and stress differ among different group of adolescents.

Table 1.1 and Mean and S.Ds of total Anxiety, Depression and Stress as a function of the type of faculty, gender and emotional intelligence.

Variable		Science		Arts	
		High EI	Low EI	High EI	Low EI
Male	Mean	11.56	12.28	6.00	14.37
	S.D	4.94	6.82	4.43	6.88
Female	Mean	12.75	14.83	15.50	9.81
	S.D	6.62	8.47	17.40	9.16

EI-Emotional Intelligence

Figure-1.1 Total Anxiety, Depression and Stress as function of Gender

Furthermore, to determine the influence of the type of faculty, gender and emotional intelligence on anxiety, depression and stress (overall) a 2x2x2 factorial analysis of variance was computed obtained result are displayed in Table 1.8.

Table 1.2 Summary of 2x2x2 (type of faculty, gender and emotional intelligence) of total Anxiety, Depression and Stress.

Source Of variance	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F-Value
Between A (Type of Faculty)	5.267	1	5.267	0.094
Between B (Gender)	406.208	1	406.208	7.219**
Between C (EIS)	262.989	1	262.989	4.674*
AxB	118.817	1	118.817	2.111
AxC	85.809	1	85.809	1.525
BxC	40.007	1	40.007	0.711
AxBxC	93.994	1	93.94	1.670
Within	6302.488	112		

N=120, **P<0.1,* P<0.5

As table 1.2 displays the significant main effect of gender [F (1,112) =7.219, .P<.01] which denote that girls (M=13.22) were found express high anxiety, depression and stress as compared to boys (M=11.05). (Fig 1.2)

Mean Score

Figure-1.2 Total Anxiety, Depression and Stress as function of Gender

Figure-1.3 Total Anxiety, Depression and Stress as a function of Emotional Intelligence

Main effect of emotional intelligence was found to be significant [$F(1,112)4.674, .P<.01$] which denote that low emotional intelligence ($M=14.73$) adolescents express high anxiety, depression and stress than high emotional intelligence group ($M=11.45$). (Fig1.3)

Discussion and Conclusion-

The purpose of present study was to investigate the effect of type of faculty, gender and emotional intelligence on Anxiety, Depression and Stress among adolescents. Results obtained on the basis of ANOVA .These findings have been interpreted and discussed in the light of a bulk of empirical evidences.

1-Impact of Type of faculty on Anxiety, Depression and Stress-

Findings of this study was to investigate the effect of type of faculty result revealed that difference between arts and Science on anxiety, depression and stress was found non significant. Present finding have contradictory result of other research finding. Research revealed that the faculty has significant effect on anxiety. The science students have high level of anxiety than arts students. (Wani, et, al.2016). Another Research revealed that engineering students have high level of anxiety than MBBS Students. (Swapna, et, al.2015). Research reported of depression among medical students. (kitu & patil, 2013). Researches also found that stress was in second year medical students and this may be due to greater fear of not attaining their goal of being a doctor. (spiel Berger CD, 1983). Some other research revealed that medical college students reported stress level (solanky et al., 2012).

2-Role of gender on anxiety, Depression and stress-

The present study was investigating the role of gender on Anxiety, Depression and stress. Result revealed that difference between boys and girls on anxiety was found non-significant. Whereas gender difference were found on depression and stress and depress than boys adolescents. Present findings have also been a number of other research findings. Research also found that female students have more depression than the male students. Results also revealed that 10th class students have high levels of depression, anxiety and stress than students of 9th and 11th standard

(Sanjiv, et al., 2010). Research showed that cases of depression is much more frequent in female students than in their male counterparts (Ghaedi and Kosnin's 2014). Some results revealed that males and female students experience different level of stress, because females are more emotional than males in reaction to their environment (Sulaiman, et al., 2009). Researchers found that female students reported higher prevalence of stress than male (Brahmbhatt, et al., 2013). Researchers found that high level of stress and more health problems in females than male. A plenty studies that reported the similar finding that female students are more stressed than male students. (Shah, et al., 2010). A sizeable number of students the importance of gender influence on stress and have consistently revealed that female reported that female reporter higher level of chronic and daily stressors than male (Hagan ,Carlson &Du 2002).

3-Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Anxiety Depression and stress–

The present study was found the effect of emotional intelligence. Result revealed that main effect of emotional intelligence on Anxiety, Depression and stress. Results revealed that difference between High and Low emotional intelligence groups on anxiety was non significant. Whereas emotional intelligence difference were found on level of depression and high stress. As findings indicate that Low emotional intelligence group excessive depress and high stress as compared to high emotional intelligence group. Researchers have found that higher Level of perceived emotional intelligence is associated with lower level of depression and physical complaints (Ciarrocchi, et al., 2002). Researches also have documented a negative association between perceived emotional intelligence and perceived stress. (pau et al., 2007) Researches revealed that the emotional intelligence is positively and significantly related to Academic achievement (Nada Abi Samra 2000). Researches suggest that emotional intelligence has the potential to offset behaviors that have been associated with higher level of morbidity and mortality. (Michel, et al., 2009).Researches have identified gender differences regarding perceived emotional intelligence early in the lifespan. (Basacki 2007). A plenty of studies showed that higher emotional intelligence was associated with better health. (Schuttet , et al., 2007)

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